

STRUCTURAL DEVELOPMENT OF THE NIMBUS-G/SEASAT-A

SMMR GRAPHITE EPOXY ANTENNA REFLECTOR

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Abstract

Specific details concerning the structural design, analysis, fabrication and testing of the Nimbus-G/Seasat-A Scanning Multichannel Microwave Radiometer (SMMR) are presented. Design requirements are illustrated and trade-off considerations discussed in terms of flight project requirements. It is shown that the application of graphite/epoxy material results in a lightweight, stiff, thermally stable antenna structure fully qualified for mission application.

Introduction

This paper presents the results of the structural development of a graphite-epoxy (Gr/E) antenna reflector for the Scanning Multi-channel Microwave Radiometer (SMMR) experiment to be launched on the GSFC NIMBUS-G/SEASAT-A earth satellite missions. The main purpose of the experiment is to perform remote sensing of the "sea state" as an aid to weather forecasting. Specifically, the SMMR experiment will evaluate passive microwave techniques for providing operationally useful ocean-surface wind speed and temperature data, polar ice canopy characteristics, and maps of atmospheric water vapor and liquid water over ocean regions.

The reflector and supporting instrument platform structure are shown in Figure 1. The relative size and placement of the SMMR with respect to the general arrangement of the NIMBUS-G satellite are shown in Figure 2. The general environment in which the SMMR reflector must operate required that it be fabricated from a material that is highly stiff, lightweight, and thermally stable; all of which characterize a graphite/epoxy material system for the reflector. Five such reflector units were fabricated and assembled by General Dynamics Convair for Microwave Research Corp., the prime contractor to JPL for the overall SMMR instrument.

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Fig. 1 - NIMBUS-G/SEASAT Scanning multichannel microwave radiometer (SMMR) experiment.

Fig. 2 - NIMBUS-G Configuration.

Description

The reflector, shown separately in Figure 3, consists of a thin offset parabolic dish continuously bonded to an I-beam backup structure which is supported in a 3-to-3 tie point configuration by six strut members from a base ring mount. All structural components of the reflector were made of Gr/E material with the exception of the base ring and strut fittings which were made of aluminum. The reflector configuration also includes tungsten masses which were used for dynamic balance. Specific construction details are provided in Ref. 1.

The reflector dish was fabricated with 5-mil thick HMS/934 tape. It consists of 6 plies laminated in a pseudoisotropic $(0/\pm 60)_S$ layup to provide an 0.76 cm (0.030 in.) thick skin. Also included in the dish configuration is an 0.102 cm (0.040 in.) thick 8 ply $(\pm 45/0_2)_S$ GY70/934 rim ring to increase the out-of-plane bending stiffness of the reflector along the periphery.

The reflector dish is adhesively bonded to a GY70/934 I-beam backup structure that consists of an interlocking assembly of 6 beam elements to form a six-point star pattern. Preliminary design efforts indicated that the six-point geometry would best satisfy the basic reflector requirements of contour surface control and dynamic stiffness. The beam members connecting the three tie points of the reflector are composed of an 0.152 cm (0.060 in.) thick 12 ply $(0/\pm(30/60)/90)_S$ laminate whereas the remaining three beam sections are made of an 0.102 cm (.040 in.) thick 8 layer $(0/45/90/-45)_S$ laminate.

The six struts are composed of GY70/934 solid octagonal sections with nominal 1.470 cm. (0.579 in.) across the flats thickness. The solid cross section was required because of high vibration induced strut loads and the RF requirement to minimize strut blockage. The octagonal configuration was decided on the basis of reduced cost of strut fabrication (as opposed to a circular cross section member). The material type was chosen to provide

Fig. 3 - SMMR Gr/E Antenna reflector.

maximum flexural bending stiffness for the reflector assembly. The ends of each strut were turned round to facilitate assembly and bonding to the metal end fittings.

The high loads generated at the support points dictated the need for metal fittings; these were machined from 2124-T851 aluminum alloy. Thermal analyses confirmed the suitability of using aluminum for the fitting components. Sufficient bond areas were required between the strut and the fitting, and the fitting and the reflector, to take out individual strut loads of approximately 1.36 MN (3,000 pounds). The kick loads associated with these high axial loads required the use of large flange bond areas between the fitting and the underside of the reflector. All bonds of the graphite/epoxy to the aluminum were made with EA 9309 adhesive.

The lower strut fittings were designed to bolt to the 0.634 cm (0.25 in.) thick machined aluminum 2124-T851 base ring which forms the interface between the reflector assembly and the instrument rotating hub mechanism. Provision was also made to mount the lower tungsten dynamic balance mass to the base ring along the plane of symmetry of the reflector. The upper balance mass was mounted to the reflector as shown in Figure 1 using an HMS/934 box beam support member. Two masses were required to dynamically balance the reflector assembly within the envelope constraints provided.

Structural Design and Analysis

The reflector was designed to meet the following structural, configurational and RF requirements:

<u>Structural</u>		<u>Configurational</u>		<u>RF</u>
Inertial loading	50g	Reflector geometry	Offset parabolid with a focal length of 45 cm	Frequency 6.6 to 37.0 GHz
Dynamic loading	5g sinusoidal at experiment interface		79 cm reflector aperture	Distortion .008 cm, rms manufacturing
Moment of Inertia	0.56 kg-m ²	Axis rotation	Tilted 42 degrees from parabolid axis	.010 cm, in orbit
Dynamically balanced	0.006 kg-m ² /sec residual angular momentum	Scan Angle	±29 degrees	
Lowest natural frequency	70 Hz			
Weight	5.70 kg (including ballast)			

In addition, the overall reflector configuration was required to satisfy a dynamic envelope condition controlled by the location of the instrument on the spacecraft (Figure 2).

In order to satisfy these requirements and assure adequate margins of safety against possible strength and stability failures, a detailed finite element model of the reflector was developed and analyzed. Representations for both the reflector assembly and the instrument mounting structure were included in the model. The finite element model (Figure 4) was used to evaluate loads, stresses, natural frequencies and weight. Early model analysis was performed using the SAP computer code whereas later analyses involving the evaluation of dynamic response were performed on NASTRAN.

Fig. 4 - Finite element model of reflector.

The geometry of the math model fully evaluated the offset paraboloid reflector geometry, joint eccentricities and backup structure to shell elastic center positions. The model consisted of 143 plate elements (both triangular and quadrilateral) and 135 bending members.

The material properties of the model accounted for the orthotropic characteristics of the various composite laminates, i.e., backup structure I-beam (caps and webs), the reflector shell, struts and counterweight tower components. Table I shows the two graphite composite systems used and their unidirectional lamina design values.

Table I. Lamina Design Analysis Properties

Property	Material	
	GY70/934	HMS/934
E_{11} MN/m ² (msi)	280,600 (40.7)	172,300 (25.0)
E_{22} MN/m ² (msi)	6,500 (.95)	11,700 (1.70)
μ	.30	.30
G MN/m ² (msi)	6,500 (.95)	4,500 (.65)
α_1 cm/cm/°C(10 ⁻⁶ in./in./°F)	-.28 (-.51)	-.25 (-.45)
α_2 cm/cm/°C(10 ⁻⁶ in./in./°F)	8.89 (16.0)	9.0 (16.2)
t cm (in.)	.013 (.005)	.006 (.0025)
σ_{11T} MN/m ² (ksi)	401.2 (58.2)	775.6 (112.5)
σ_{11C} MN/m ² (ksi)	401.2 (58.2)	568.8 (82.5)
σ_{22T} MN/m ² (ksi)	13.1 (1.9)	48.2 (7.0)
σ_{22C} MN/m ² (ksi)	142.7 (20.7)	215.8 (31.3)

The model was first analyzed for the case of a 50g quasi static acceleration loading individually applied in all three orthogonal S/C coordinate directions. Maximum stress of 91.7 MN/m² (13.3 ksi) was found to occur in a reflector strut near its attachment to the base ring support. Approximately 55% of this stress was derived from strut bending. Using a design ultimate strength of 310.2 MN/m² (45.0 ksi) as determined from compression tests of strut specimens resulted in a margin of safety of approximately 3.5 against strut failure due to such inertial loading.

A separate model analysis was then made which indicated that first resonance of the structure should occur in lateral bending in the plane of symmetry at a frequency of 88 Hz. Subsequent development testing of the Antenna Test Model (ATM) discussed below resulted in an actual fundamental resonance of 59 Hz in the predicted mode of vibration. The disparity between analysis predictions and test results is due mainly to differences in mass modeling between the actual instrument 5.62 kg (12.40 lb) and that of the model 4.49 kg (9.89 lb) at the time of design development and analysis. A subsequent model improvement and analysis iteration resulted in a predicted system fundamental resonance of 77 Hz, but no attempt was made to further improve analysis/test correlation.

Finally, the math model was analyzed for internal loads and structural response due to a specified lateral 5g sinusoidal forcing function applied at the base of the structure. This analysis resulted in the highest predicted stresses throughout the instrument. As a result of loads generated by this analysis, detailed features of the reflector design as described previously were changed to improve overall structural performance. The analysis was based on an assumed structural damping factor of 1.5% of critical damping which was considered conservative based on previous S/C component test experience (e.g. Ref. 2, 3). A summary of the stresses induced at several critical locations in the structure due to ultimate loads is given in Table II.

Table II. Reflector Stresses Due to 5 g Sinusoidal Base Motion

Location	Max. Stress MN/m ² (psi)	Allowable Stress MN/m ² (psi)	Stress Type
Dish	19.3 (2,800)	20.0 (2,900)	Shear
Rim ring	286.8 (41,600) 244.7 (35,500)	310.2 (45,000) 262.0 (38,000)	Strength Crippling
Back-up structure	235.8 (34,200) 235.8 (34,200) 9.8 (1,420)	310.2 (45,000) 244.7 (35,500) 10.3 (1,500)	Strength Crippling Glue shear
Struts	247.5 (35,900)	310.2 (45,000)	Strength
Strut fittings	10.3 (1,490)	10.3 (1,500)	Glue Shear
Base ring	118.6 (17,200)	314.4 (45,600)	Strength

The above results also include separate calculations which were made to assess joint strength and strut stability. The joint analysis considered the complex nature of intersecting skewed members and the frequency and phase angle relationship of the various member's loads.

Fabrication

Based on the design analysis results, detailed fabrication drawings and specifications were prepared and five reflector units fabricated. Tooling for the reflector structure was designed to allow for fabrication of all antennas without tool replacement or repair.

The reflector dish assembly was fabricated from computer-developed gore sections which facilitated layup and provided the desired offset parabolic contour. An eight-ply pseudoisotropic layup of 2.5-mil HMS/934 material was initially considered for its reduced weight benefit and reduced thermal distortional effects. Because basic material and layup cost became the prime factors in material selection, the eight-ply orientation was eliminated in favor of the six-ply configuration described previously. The dish was fabricated in an autoclave oven with careful control so as to achieve uniform constant dish thickness.

Layup of the rim ring was done using a fairly conventional gore segment approach. Ten-degree ring arc segments were cut and individually hand-pressed in place to form an angle rim. Once one complete layer was positioned,

a subsequent layer was added, but staggered about one degree with respect to the prior layer. Thus, no splice lines up in the layers that formed the graphite/epoxy rim ring.

Other than miscellaneous clips, brackets, and gussets, the only remaining composite hardware item on the reflector is the struts. The octagonal struts, which account for approximately 20 percent of the total reflector assembly weight, were to be initially tubular; but high loads, high natural frequency (70 Hz), and a total diameter limitation of 5/8 inch dictated a need for a solid strut.

A design-to-cost decision was made after a study to determine ways of procuring or making these struts. Procurement of a pultruded rod material was briefly investigated, but the need for an ultra-high modulus fiber (GY-70), and an approved resin system that met outgassing requirements, eliminated this approach. Developing a method to mold the struts was discounted as extremely costly and risky considering the schedule problems that might occur.

The method decided upon was straightforward and low cost. It consisted simply of laying up and curing large, flat plate stock of GY 70/934. The plate was ripped into long square bars and the bars chamfered along their square corners to form octagons about 5/8 inches at their maximum width. The ends of each strut were turned round so that a uniform gap could be obtained where struts fit into the metal fittings. The machining cost for these struts proved to be minimal, and in addition allowed straightness requirements to be maintained.

After individual component fabrication, the reflector dish and backup structure were assembled and profilometer measurements taken to determine RF surface accuracy (Ref. 1). Final reflector assembly was then made using a rigid assembly fixture as shown in Figure 5. Its function was to accurately locate the reflector dish in the proper position above the base ring. Focal point location was later accomplished by shimming the reflector subassembly relative to the hub of the mounting platform structure. After full assembly,

Fig. 5 - Reflector assembly fixture.

spin balance tests were run on each unit to ensure that the reflector structure satisfied dynamic balance requirements.

A summary of the weights computed for each reflector unit is given in Table III. Because mass property analysis was not carried through the entire program, some approximations were made in order to complete this table. The final weights recorded for each unit and the basic design differences in each unit follow logically so that for purposes of comparison, this table is considered technically correct.

Table III. Reflector Assembly Weight Summary

Component	Weight kg (lbs)				
	Unit #1	Unit #2	Unit #3	Unit #4	Unit #5
Reflector Skin	0.738 (1.63)	0.748 (1.65)	0.748 (1.65)	0.744 (1.64)	0.738 (1.63)
Backup Structure*	1.633	1.547	1.819	1.846	1.814
Top Flange	(3.60)	(3.41)	(4.01)	(4.07)	(4.00)
Bottom Flange					
Eggcrate					
Rim Ring					
C'wt Mount					
Detail Parts					
Metal Components	0.844	0.866	0.857	0.848	0.875
Strut Fittings	(1.86)	(1.91)	(1.89)	(1.87)	(1.93)
Base Ring					
Struts (6)	1.025 (2.26)	1.052 (2.32)	1.043 (2.30)	1.043 (2.30)	1.039 (2.29)
Counterweights	1.742	1.411	1.560	1.519	1.519
Reflector	(3.84)	(3.11)	(3.44)	(3.35)	(3.35)
Base					
Total	5.529 (12.19)	5.625 (12.40)	6.028 (13.29)	6.001 (13.23)	5.987 (13.20)
*Denotes approximate value					

The additional weight that brought Unit #3 up to 6.028 kg (13.29 lbs) and therefore beyond the weight requirements is a result of the redesign that occurred after joint failures which were encountered during ATM vibration development testing discussed below. Approximately 0.317 kg (0.70 lbs) of graphite/epoxy parts were added. These parts and the additional required ballast material (0.091 kg (0.20 lbs) approx.) account for the 0.408 kg (0.90 lb) increase in weight of Unit #3 over Unit #2 (ATM).

Testing

All testing was performed on the ATM unit which was considered representative of the SMMR series of reflector assemblies. After assembly and dynamic spin balancing of the ATM unit, it was first subjected to low level (0.2g rms) sinusoidal frequency sweep testing to determine fundamental structural resonances. Sweeps were made in three orthogonal directions from 5 to 2000 Hz at a sweep rate of one octave/minute. Based on accelerometer data taken during the sweeps, the X, Y, and Z axis lowest natural frequencies were found to be 68, 80 and 116 Hz, respectively. The lowest resonant frequency of 68 Hz in the X direction satisfied within experimental tolerance the specification requirement of 70 Hz.

The ATM unit was next mounted to the instrument support platform (Figure 1) and the entire assembly subjected to three axis sinusoidal vibration development testing to protoflight qualification levels. The test level requirements were as follows:

<u>Direction</u>	<u>Frequency (Hz)</u>	<u>Amplitude (g pk)</u>
Transverse	5-2000	5.0
Thrust	5-25	7.0
	25-200	6.0
	200-2000	5.0

Sweep rate = 4.0 octaves/minute

The test setup is shown in Figure 6. A low-level (1g) X axis sine sweep was conducted to determine the first order fundamental resonant frequency and associated maximum gain of the unit at resonance. Resonant vibration occurred in the predicted lateral bending mode at a fundamental frequency of 59 Hz (vs a best predicted frequency of 77 Hz). A gain factor of approximately 10 at the top of the reflector strut members was determined from

Fig. 6 - SMMR vibration test setup.

acceleration response measurements. This loads amplification factor is equivalent to a structural damping coefficient (percent of critical damping) of approximately 5% (vs 1.5% used to derive the response stresses shown in Table I.). The relatively large experimental damping factor is attributable mainly to increased system damping provided by the slide plate and shaker.

In attempting to test the unit to full scale X axis sine levels, a failure of the reflector joint in the vicinity of the attachment of the forward struts to the reflector was encountered. This failure occurred at approximately 54 Hz during loads build up prior to reaching structural resonance. The maximum stress developed in the struts at failure was 14,800 psi. Immediately prior to failure, however, the maximum stress level was 9000 psi. The failure was determined to be a delamination of the upper part of the joint in a peel type failure mode. A field repair of the failed joint was made in order that the test program be completed. The repair was similarly applied to the opposite strut-reflector joint as a preventative measure.

Testing then resumed with a 5-g sweep, notched however to 3 g's from 45 to 75 Hz in the area of resonance. The potential use of notching to the 3-g level during lateral vibration of the unit had been discussed previously with S/C and GSFC personnel and technically determined to be a satisfactory lower bound on S/C derived base input g-level excitation. Such notching was implemented at this time based on project requirements relating to scheduled hardware delivery of the ATM unit for evaluation during spacecraft vibration testing. During the sweep a second joint failure was encountered at approximately 54 Hz. The failure occurred in the vicinity of the base attachment of the upper ballast mast to the reflector. The failure was found to be a delamination of the joint in a peel type failure mode. A field repair to the ballast mast was made in order to allow testing to be completed.

It should be noted that both field repairs were made to simulate as nearly as possible the probable joint redesign configurations. The repairs were made after close visual inspection of the failed areas and evaluation of the experimental response data. A best effort approach, supported by hand calculation analyses, was used to determine the final repair configurations.

Full scale testing was resumed and the remainder of the vibration test program completed satisfactorily. Completion of all sinusoidal testing within the allotted test schedule was important in order to evaluate the response behavior of structural components other than the reflector. The results of the sinusoidal test program are summarized in Table IV.

The data for each element of Table IV consists of the maximum response value (right side of element) and the associated frequency (left side of element) obtained during the test. Channels SG1 through SG4 present stress response data (psi) whereas the remaining channels indicate peak acceleration g-levels. A modulus of elasticity value of 45×10^6 psi, derived from strut specimen testing, was used to convert strain gage data to stress results. As indicated for the column of Z axis data, a flat 5 g (notched) sweep was made in place of the originally specified test level requirements.

After the vibration development test, the reflector-strut joint and the upper ballast mast-reflector joint were redesigned in a conservative manner and analyzed to ensure design integrity. The joint redesign configurations were similar to the repairs made to the ATM unit and resulted in the increased assembly weight shown for units 3, 4 and 5 of Table III. Instrument sinusoidal qualification testing of unit 3 containing the redesigned joint configurations was successfully completed and is discussed below.

Table IV. ATM Development Vibration Test
Results Frequency-Response Data

Channel Description	S A X I S I O R S	X axis - 5g				Y axis 5g (N)		Z axis 5g (N)	
		5-54 Hz		75-2000 Hz 2000-75 Hz		5-2000 Hz 2000-5 Hz		5-2000 Hz 2000-5 Hz	
S/G #1	Z	54	9800**(6700)	350	6300	58	4200	273	2200
S/G #2	Z	54	8400**(7900)	275	2800	61	5600	273	2800
S/G #3	Z	54	14800**(9000)	275	3500	58	5600	273	2800
S/G #4	Z	54	2100**(1800)	-	-	61	1400	-	-
Top of Strut	Y	54	125*	340	37	61	56	210	37
Top of Strut	Z	54	125*	210	25	61	19	210	37
Wave Guide	X	54	62	240	180	230	187	1375	312
Upper Ballast	X	54	50	310	50	60	25	210	125
Upper Ballast	Y	54	15	210	94	114	75	450	62
Upper Ballast	Z	54	42	290	56	60	25	210	175
Reflector Tip	Z	54	50	260	187	310	44	210	175
Reflector Tip	Z	54	75	290	50	60	31	210	94
Top Rear Strut	Z	54	-	290	31	650	16	510	38
Lower Ballast	Z	54	-	310	38	580	38	580	50
Motor Web	Z	54	-	310	12	560	25	610	75
Cal Horn	X	54	-	430	62	164	44	1690	280
Cal Horn	Z	54	-	360	31	60	38	210	47

LEGEND: Xg(N) = Notched g run
 * = Readings beyond gain setting of 100 g
 - = Reading too small
 ** = Max. reading at reflector-strut joint failure
 () = Readings immediately prior to failure

Concurrent with the joint redesign activity, and owing to instrument schedule delivery requirements, a decision was made to use the repaired ATM unit for S/C vibration qualification testing. The rationale was based on the expected low g instrument base inputs from S/C vibration and the preliminary joint redesign data that indicated that the repaired ATM unit and the final redesigned reflector assembly would be structurally equivalent. Accordingly, the ATM was shipped to GE-STC and successfully passed the S/C sinusoidal qualification vibration test. During this test, the base input to the SMMR instrument never exceeded 3.0 g's. The results of this test were used to substantiate the use of notching to 3.0 g's in the area of resonance during the transverse sweeps as revised instrument qualification test levels. Maximum response data obtained during S/C vibration at key locations on the instrument are given in Table V with a comparison of previous response data obtained

Table V. Maximum Peak Acceleration and Corresponding Frequency Response Data of SMMR during S/C Nimbus-G Sinusoidal Qualification Test and Comparison with ATM Response Data*

Channel Description	Sensor Axis	S/C Qualification Test						ATM Test (Notched)					
		X		Y		Z		X		Y		Z	
ATM shaker input	X							45-75	3.0				
ATM shaker input	Y									45-80	3.0		
ATM shaker input	Z											All	5.0
SMMR-S/C interface	X	66	2.8										
SMMR-S/C interface	Y			56	1.9								
SMMR-S/C interface	Z					56	2.6						
Upper ballast	X	55	34	56	8	56	19	57	37	60	25	66	27
Upper ballast	Y			116	31	112	44			114	75	122	46
Upper ballast	Z	56	27	58	7	56	14	57	53	60	25	210	175
Top of strut	Z	56	17	61	14	56	15	57	31	61	19	210	37

*Data for each element of Table V consists of the acceleration g level response (right side of element) and associated frequency (left side of element).

during notched sinusoidal vibration development testing of the ATM unit. The comparison shows that in all cases S/C qualification testing resulted in lower g levels than those experienced by the unit under instrument notched-level vibration testing.

After joint redesign and implementation on the remaining reflector assemblies (units 3, 4 and 5), unit 3 was subjected to qualification sinusoidal vibration testing. The qualification test specification was revised as follows:

<u>Direction</u>	<u>Frequency (Hz)</u>	<u>Amplitude (g pk)</u>
Transverse	5-100	3.0
	100-200	0.5
Thrust	5-24	5.0
	25-100	6.0
	100-200	0.5

The unit was mounted to the instrument support platform and the final assembly tested in the same manner as the development vibration test. The test was successful with observed dynamic behavior similar to that of the preceding sinusoidal tests. The results of the qualification test, which was performed with reduced instrumentation coverage, are shown in Table VI.

Table VI. Instrument Qualification
Vibration Test Results

Frequency-Response Data							
Channel Description	Sensor Axis	X axis		Y axis		Z axis	
Top of strut	Z	61	18	64	23	45	3
Upper ballast	X	61	47	64	18	82	2
Upper ballast	Y	69	6	64	37	59	1
Upper ballast	Z	61	28	64	11	85	5

As before, the data for each element of Table VI consists of the maximum response value (right side of element) and the associated frequency (left side of element) obtained during the test. First resonance occurred during the X axis sweep at 61 Hz. The slight increase in this fundamental resonance value above that of the development test (59 Hz) is due to increased joint stiffness provided by the redesigned configuration. The gain values, however, were very similar to those obtained during the development test.

Conclusions

As a result of the combined analytical and experimental effort described above, the Gr/E antenna reflector assembly was structurally qualified for flight application on the Nimbus-G/SEASAT-A spacecraft missions. During this successful effort many engineering trade offs and difficult technical decisions were made to keep the structural program costs to a minimum. Maximum

effort was made to utilize experimental data to guide the design/analysis portion of the assembly structural development. This approach, supported by the insight provided by limited computer model analyses concerning the dynamic behavior of the structure, proved sufficient to achieve the program structural qualification goals.

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